

Isolation, Identification and Organic Production of Mushrooms *Ganoderma lucidum* (Curt.:Fr) Karst (Reishi)

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Abstract: The present study is first record of the isolation, identification and fruiting body production of the Reishi mushroom (*Ganoderma lucidum* (W. Curt.: Fr.) P. Karst) from the Iraqi environment (RMI). The fungus was isolated from a mushroom associated with dead pomegranate tree. The growth of the RMI on Potato Dextrose Agar was dense, white and remarkably fast. Spawn prepared from the RMI used to inoculate two kinds of sawdust, unknown source (obtained from a carpentry workshop) and of pomegranate trunk. Each type of sawdust after moistening was amended with 5% of the wetted wheat bran (based on dry weight) and sterilized by autoclaving in polyethylene bags. Bags were inoculated with 3% spawn and incubated at 28 ± 3 °Cs. Fungal growth completed on pomegranate sawdust bags after 10 days, while it took 22 days to complete on the other sawdust. The RMI colonized bags were exposed to light (LED 30W) for 6 hours during the night in addition to the daylight hours and to 65-80% relative humidity. The RMI growth stages were recorded by digital imaging until fruiting bodies ripened as indicated by basidiospores release. The mushroom reached maturation in 50 days on pomegranate sawdust while 65 days on other sawdust culture. The morphological properties of the RMI and its anatomical, taste and molecular characteristics were all consistent with that describe for *Ganoderma lucidum*. Phylogenetically, sequence data from nuclear internal transcribed spacer regions (ITS) confirmed that the RMI showed significant alignment with 573/573 (100%) identity for *Ganoderma lucidum* (KT3433161).

Keywords: Reishi, *Ganoderma lucidum*, Organic production, Molecular identification

Fungi have special concerns in humankind's life since the ancient era because of their pathogenic properties, distinct nutritional and pharmacological values and their role in the ecological balance (Lange et al 2012). The therapeutic properties of the mushrooms have been recognized from prehistoric times and recently they have become more important, especially the mushroom known as Reishi or red mushroom (*Ganoderma lucidum* (W. Curt.: Fr.) P. Karst) and belongs to the phylum Basidiomycota, order Aphyllophorales and family Ganodermataceae (Polyporaceae). It is diagnosed as facultative parasite attacks wide host range up to 144 species of fruit and forest trees (Fernando 2008, Naher 2013). The Reishi mushroom has a distinguished status among the ancient Chinese and Japanese because they believed that the Reishi mushroom gives eternity, reinforces youth and promotes health. Recently the Reishi mushroom also has considered as being the most valuable mushroom, known for human due to its effectiveness as an anti-cancer, anti-HIV, anti- heart attack, anti-diabetes, and as a panacea (American Herbal Pharmacopoeia 2000, Wachtel-Galor et al 2011, Hapuarachchi et al 2018).

Reishi production and trading become common in recent years. Several companies have been specialized in manufacturing of various pharmaceuticals, food supplements and cosmetics (creams, marijuana, shampoos

and toothpastes) from such mushroom. The commercial value of Reishi mushroom products reached more than US\$ 2.5 billion in Asia alone (Li et al 2013). The annual production of Reishi as reported lately in China alone was about 110000 metric tons (Hapuarachchi et al 2018). Trading with Reishi is reported in 85 countries and there are about 100 brands under which about 780 Reishi products are marketed (Lai 2004, Li 2016, Wachtel-Galor et al 2011). The Reishi fruit body contains about 400 secondary metabolites of various chemical groups (polysaccharides, terpenes, steroids, phenols, nucleosides, peptidoglycans, proteins and vitamins) which attribute to the therapeutic importance of the mushroom (Wachtel-Galor et al 2011). In Iraq, despite the remarkable increases in production of edible mushrooms, no report has been found in production of Reishi except one study in 2017 reported that *Ganoderma lucidum* among several other macro fungi found in the province of Salah al-Din (Al-Khesraji et al 2017). The objectives of this research are to investigate the presence and identify of the Reishi mushroom in Iraqi environment and explore the possibility of organic production of the isolated mushroom.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samples collection: The social networking was used in collection of macro fungi. Among the received mushrooms

fruiting bodies, one was selected in this study because it resembles the *Ganoderma* spp. in light of its description in the literatures (American Herbal Pharmacopoeia 2000, Wang et al 2012, Nithya et al 2014, Hennicke et al 2016 and Bhosle et al 2010). The mushroom was collected from stem of dead pomegranate tree. In addition, a sample of three-dried Reishi mushrooms were bought from a local herbalist's shop. For isolation from the selected Iraqi mushroom small pieces of the interior tissue of the upper surface of the mushroom cap were cultured on sterile Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) (Nithya et al 2014) at $28\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$. The grew isolated fungus named as RMI.

Spawn preparation: Wheat grains were used to prepare the spawn (Behnam and Naser 2008) were washed, boiled for 25 minutes, and left in boiling water for another 25 minutes. The boiled grains were filtered and spread in a light layer to remove excess water. Calcium sulfate and carbonate were added at 20 and 15 g/ kg of the grain respectively. The mixture was distributed in glass bottles of 300 ml, autoclaved and repeated autoclaving on the following day. Bottles were inoculated with three disks of 5mm diameter mycelium from the RMI culture under laminar flow cabinet and incubated at $28\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Mushroom production: The possibility of the RMI to produce mushroom on cellulosic plant wastes was carried out as per standard procedure (Roy et al 2015, Erkel 2009). Two wood sawdust prepared from dead pomegranate stems and another of unknown wood source (obtained from a carpentry workshop). Both types of the sawdust were soaked tap water for 24 hours and amended with 5% wheat bran (based on dry weight that previously moistened in water). Each mixture of sawdust was distributed in polyethylene bags (size 5 kg) replicated three times. The bags were closed with one opening that was closed with cotton plug. The bags were sterilized by autoclaving for hours were inoculated with 3% spawn and incubated temperature of $28\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$. After the fungus has completed grow on the entire content of the bags, bags were provided with light for 6 hours at night with LED (30W) fixed at 60-70 cm above the bags in addition to the light of the day hours. Incubation at more than 65 % relative humidity provided with air cooler and reached 80% immediately after atomizing with a hand atomizer (more than once a day) (Roy et al 2015). Stages of the fungal growth and their durations were recorded and documented by digital photography.

The mushroom produced from RMI was identified morphologically based on shape, color and texture of the mushroom, upper and lower its cap's nature, presence and absence and nature of the stalk (stipe) (American Herbal Pharmacopoeia 2000, Wang et al 2012, Nithya et al 2014,

Hennicke 2016, Bhosle et al 2010). The mushroom phenotypic identification also was supported by an anatomical study of the mushroom tissue, basidiospores and basidia shape and color, and hyphal types (American Herbal Pharmacopoeia 2000, Singh et al 2014). In addition, mushroom taste was recorded by a panel. Each one of the panels requested to chew small pieces of the mushroom (without prior identification of what material or taste) and collect their opinions on the taste. Moreover, the identification is confirmed phylogenetically.

RMI molecular characteristics: The total DNA of the RMI produced mushroom and the imported Reishi mushroom samples were extracted in Wahaj DNA laboratory in Bagdad, Iraq using Fungal/Bacterial/ Yeast DNA MiniPrep kit (Irvin, CA, USA). Both mushroom samples were surface disinfected with 5% H_2O_2 , labeled and ground with electrical grinder. The extracted DNA, followed the manufacturer's instructions was quantified by UV spectrophotometry (Beckman DU-50 Spectrophotometer, Germany) and checked by agarose gel electrophoresis.

DNA amplification and sequencing: ITS was conducted using a couple of specific primers, ITS1 (5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3') as forward and ITS4 (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3') as a reverse primer (Integrated DNA Technologies company IDT, Canada).

The PCR amplification was performed in a total volume of 25 μl containing 1.5 μl DNA, 5 μl Taq PCR PreMix (Intron, Korea), 1 μl of each primer (10 pmol) then nuclease-free distilled water was added to bring the volume to 25 μl . The PCR conditions were as follows: Denaturation at 94°C for 3 min, followed by 35 cycles of 94°C for 45s, 52°C for 1 min and 72°C for 1 min with final extension at 72°C for 7 min using a thermal Cycler (Gene Amp, PCR system 9700; Applied Biosystem). The PCR products were separated on 1.5% agarose gel and visualized under 302 nm UV light (the device information) after staining with red dye (Intron Korea). The PCR product of ITS region was sequenced at Microgen Co. (Macrogen Inc., Korea) using of ABI 3730 Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, USA).

The sequence processing was performed using MEGA6 (Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis version 6.0) software and the molecular identification was conducted using Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) software which is available online at the National Center of Biotechnology Information, NCBI (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results revealed that various kinds of macro fungi thrive during autumn and spring season in Iraqi (Fig. 1 and 2).

Among the non-edible mushrooms associated with a dead pomegranate tree which selected according to its appearance most likely resemble *Ganoderma spp.* (Alexopoulos 1996) (Fig. 2) and its association with dead fruit tree (which most likely to be a pathogen killed the tree) (Fernando, 2008 and Naher 2013). The sample of the dried mushroom obtained from the local herb store which marketed as Reishi mushroom (Fig. 3) was identical in shape and color to the *Ganoderma lucidum* (Bhosle et al 2010, Nithya et al 2014, Hennicke et al 2016, Bhosle et al 2010). Culturing results of the RMI on the PDA revealed a white, rich growth mycelium (Fig. 4) characterized by rapid and dense growth (full the petri dish of 9 cm diameter at $28\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ within 5 days). On the other hand the isolated mycelium colonized the whole wheat grain at $28\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the spawn was ready within 14 days.

Growing the RMI on sawdust showed different growth rates on the different kinds of the sawdust culture according to its source. The RMI grew faster on pomegranate sawdust. The fungus colonized the pomegranate bags within 10 days, while it took 22 days on another. The initiation of the

mushroom fruiting body was observed after 15 and 28 days in pomegranate and unknown sawdust respectively from the day of inoculation. The first signs of the fruiting body were appeared as a cream-colored tissue and the primordia were white to creamy colored, which later turned to yellow than to a reddish yellow color (Fig. 5). The completely grown RMI mushroom appeared of close to circle cap with a clear stalk of lactate sharp red (Fig. 6).

After the mushrooms were fully developed and matured, they began to release huge numbers of basidiospores. The released basidiospores appeared as a brown colored powder that accumulated on the surface of the mushrooms and surfaces of their culturing bags (Fig. 7). The size of the mushroom formed in bags of pomegranate sawdust was larger and early matured compared to that formed in the bags of the other sawdust. The superiority of the pomegranate sawdust as indicated by the rapid colonization of the substrate and the time of mushroom development and size is most likely because of its homogeneity or its nutrient content or lacking of possible growth inhibitors. These results agree with the previous finding of agricultural wastes on the

Fig. 1. Various non- usual edible mushrooms (macro fungi) collected from different locations in Iraq

Fig. 2. Selected mushroom (RMI) for study in this research

Fig. 3. Reishi mushroom sold at the local herb store

Fig. 4. (1) Mycelium growth of the RMI on potato dextrose agar and (2) Spawn prepared of the RMI on wheat grains

Fig. 5. Stages of the RMI grown on pomegranate sawdust. (A and B) Complete colonization on pomegranate sawdust, (c and d) A fungal tissue form on the upper side of the culturing bag mouths, (E and F) Primordia appearance of fruiting body

nature of the growth the Reishi mushroom (Singh et al 2014, Roy et al 2015).

The morphological examinations of the produced mushroom revealed that the shape, color, and mushroom parts resemble the *Ganoderma lucidum* (American Herbal Pharmacopoeia 2000, Wang et al 2012, Nithya et al 2014, Hennicke et al 2016, Bhosle et al 2010, Shilpi 2018). The results also indicated that mushroom fruit body was soft, spongy and then harden to be wooden of white colored at the beginning and changed gradually to red, reddish brown (Figs. 6 and 7).

The outer surface of the cap and the stalk are bright red and the lower surface of the cap was white, turns yellow and then brown. Furthermore, the anatomical examinations of the produced mushroom RMI also matched that of *Ganoderma lucidum* description. The basidiospores are characterized by a brown oval shaped of double walls in which the inner wall is dark brown and the outer is transparent. The inner wall also contains protrusions or thorns that protrude from the outer wall, giving the spore a coarse appearance and truncate at the apex (Fig. 8).

In this study three kinds of hyphae were distinguished in

the produced Reishi mushroom, namely skeletal, binding and generative hyphae (Fig. 9). Examination of the lower surface of the Reishi mushroom cap showed the pores of regular circular to ovoid shape and more often neighboring pores were fused (Fig. 10). This agreed with what was previously study for *Ganoderma lucidum* (Hennicke et al 2016).

The basidia are transparent and undivided (Fig. 10). The morphological characters of the RMI agreed with that what described before for *Ganoderma lucidum*. The results of the tasting panel revealed that the mushroom was of bitter taste and this is also the conformation for identification of the RMI as *Ganoderma lucidum* as has been reported for bitterness (American Herbal Pharmacopoeia 2000).

The DNA was successfully extracted from the two mushroom samples as indicated by the electropherogram, which showed a distinct band of the both mushroom samples. (DNA purity = $OD_{260} / OD_{280} \geq 1.8$). Reads ranged between 1 and 2). The final DNA concentration was adjusted to 50 ng/ ul. PCR amplifications of total genomic DNA of the two samples produced a single PCR product of approximated molecular sizes were about 550bp using molecular weight marker plus DNA Ladder. The sequence analyses in this study for the RMI showed significant alignment with 573/573 (100%) identity for *G. lucidum* (KT3433161). The sequence analyses for the imported Reishi Mushroom showed significant alignment and

Fig. 6. Developmental stages of the RMI fruiting body on pomegranate sawdust. 1, 2 and 3: Primordia development, 4: Lower surface of the mushroom cap 5: Complete fruiting body mushroom

Fig. 7. 1: Mature mushroom of the RMI. 2: Large number of basidiospores accumulated under the mushroom cap

Fig. 8. Appearance of the RMI fruiting body and their basidiospores. A1 and A2: mature mushroom fruiting body liberated a large number of basidiospores (brown layer on the surface of the bag), B1- B6: Basidiospores under microscope with different magnifications (1-6) up to 1000 X

Fig. 9. Anatomy of the RMI. 1: Cells of the outer tissue of the mushroom's cap, 2: Skeletal hyphae, 3: Binding hyphae

Fig. 10. Larger images X400 of the RMI mushroom tissues: A: (1) hymenium-lined layer of tubing, which carrying the basidiospores and (2) the lower surface of the capillary cap containing the openings of the tubes from which the basidiospores are released. B: canals openings that are mostly round or fused to form elongated open shape. C: The layer of fertile lining of the tubes carrying the ovoid transparent basidia

573/575 (99.0%) for *G. lucidum* (MN240471.1). Based on sequence similarity to corresponding sequences in the Gen Bank the two mushrooms are identical and identified as *G. lucidum*.

CONCLUSION

This study is first record of the isolation of the Reishi mushroom (*G. lucidum* (W. Curt.: Fr.) P. Karst) from the Iraqi environment. The morphological properties of the fungus and its anatomical, taste and molecular characteristics were all consistent with that describe for *G. lucidum*. Phylogenetically, sequence data from nuclear internal transcribed spacer regions (ITS) confirmed that and showed significant alignment with 573/573 (100%) identity for *G. lucidum* (KT3433161). The growth of the fungus on Potato Dextrose Agar was dense, white and remarkably fast. The mushroom reached maturation in 50 days on pomegranate sawdust. The first signs of the fruiting body were appeared as a cream-colored tissue and the primordia of white to creamy colored, which later turned to yellow than to sharp red color. The completely mushroom appeared of close to circle cap with a clear stalk of lactate sharp red. The organic production of the Reishi mushroom on agricultural wastes is easy simple and inexpensive way.

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